

>CIX26

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>CIX1043

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>CIX1044

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>CIX1045

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>CIX1046

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>CIX1047

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>CIX1048

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>CIX1049

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>CIX1050

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>BLS256

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GCTGCTGGACGAGG CCAAGAAAGGCCGCCAGGTCCAGCGCTTCAAGGGCCTGGGCGAAATGAACG

Figure S1 : Partial sequence of the *gyrB* housekeeping gene for the 9 investigated and reference BLS256 *Xoc* strains